

APPLICATION OF DESIGN TECHNOLOGY TO THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS AND WAYS OF FORMING LEADERSHIP IN STUDENTS THROUGH IT

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Abstract: This article talks about the introduction of design technology to education and the development of leadership qualities in young students through it.

Key words: Educational process, design, technologies, method, students' cognitive process, education of foreign countries.

As a result of the introduction of design technology into the educational process, productive activity occurs between the student and the teacher. Because project technology is based on advance planning of education, knowing its outcome in advance.

Project technology appeared in the USA in the 20s of the 20th century and was first introduced into the teaching process as a project method or a problem-based method. According to the stylists, this method helps to correctly, purposefully and systematically direct the educational activities of learners. Along with keeping in mind that modern pedagogical technologies cover the entire pedagogical process with its name, the Russian scientist V.P. Bepalko "...didactic technologies of a new nature used in education serve as a certain tool. This paradigm creates a new system of scientific and practical pedagogical activity." - as a rule, it is appropriate to know his opinions.

1. Each educational technology is specific for a certain purpose and for a certain type of education, including the design technology, which is primarily the development of students' independent thinking and decision-making skills. serves for The basis of design technology is also the perspective of answers to questions such as why the project was created and where it can be used. This technology makes it possible to plan and forecast the stages of the educational process in advance by promoting forward thinking, thoughts, and ideas.

The design method allows students to:

- finding and solving problems, finding a target in the flow of information, bringing together knowledge in various fields of science;
- using the right to choose activities, to put forward different ideas, to identify such things as analysis;
- to be responsible for the results of one's activities, to make independent decisions, to identify and correct achievements and shortcomings;
- scientific estimation of the results of various solutions, proposals;
- work in a team encourages participation in the discussion of different points of view.

From the above, it can be seen that the basis of design technology is the formation of an independent opinion and the implementation of ideas. These aspects are closely related to the development of leadership in young people. At this point, leadership is the ability to follow one's own thoughts and ideas, to exercise leadership in team work. Leadership development is shaped in different ways in different layers of society, so it requires uniqueness in the

educational process. In particular, the importance of practical classes in developing leadership skills among students of higher educational institutions is incomparable. In particular, if we take into account that in the series of practical classes, the main activity is performed by students, and the teacher is only a supervisor, a favorable environment is created for the implementation of design work and the creation of leadership in it. The use of design technology in teaching processes allows students to have an individual and differentiated approach. Aspects covered by the method in the process of implementation are also elements that are considered constant and important, and they consist of:

- The structure of the project should be well worked out;
- Research subject, relevance, social importance, used methods, conducting experiments for the participants participating in the project.

When considering the example of leadership design technologies, it is appropriate to do the following:

- through an individual approach to each student, aspects of his/her aptitude for a certain subject, industry network are determined;
- a group of students with a similar level of knowledge is formed and the most relevant and important aspects of the topic are selected;
- a scheme for project work is created within the selected topics;
- teams think and plan the project together;
- the intended result of the project work is analyzed.

During the implementation of all works, along with the enrichment of the project in content and form, the students who have priority in the leadership of thoughts and ideas in the group will stand out. This process is the process of emergence of leadership.

It is also very important to ensure student activity in new educational projects in the formation of youth leadership. For example, in F.R. Avazov's article on "Youth leadership and the ways of its formation", he emphasized that in the implementation of youth leadership, the inclusion of projects aimed at involving active, initiative, leading individuals from different layers of society in the educational processes for them will have a good effect, emphasizing through the following sentences "this method of forming leadership is very exclusive and is very important to invite young people who have good knowledge and skills but are shy to leadership activities," he said.

At the core of the design technologies, it is possible to distinguish the most active among students, along with making innovations in science. The most active in all aspects can predict the expected result even when the topic of the project is defined. During the implementation of this method, future professional qualities and skills of preparation for social and professional environment are developed in students. The knowledge and practical skills acquired by the students in the classes organized on the basis of the design method will also prepare them for the design classes organized with individuals in their future practical pedagogical or social activities. Another important aspect is that the activities related to the design activity are aimed at realizing the individual development of students, the ability to self-evaluate their behavior objectively.

Any type of training in the design category creates conditions for students to use their potential and reveal their undiscovered hidden abilities. During the work on any carefully developed projects, new talents, gaps in some students, aspects of priority in some are revealed. Leader students not only show their priorities, in addition to this, during the design

work, they give explanations to their peers who are passive in a specific field of science and encourage them to be active in the next projects. To students who differ in terms of talent, group leaders assign each of them suitable tasks in the distribution of work, which forms the skills of being able to claim leadership in the areas specific to their talents in other students. So, if the educational activity is considered as a coherent and integrated system, then it would be appropriate to select the design technologies that are introduced to it in such a way as to bring out all the possibilities and talents of the students. Development of leadership aspects of students and young people is also carried out on the basis of these works. In making leadership the most necessary element among young people, working based on the following recommendations also guarantees a positive result:

- to establish the use of design technologies within each discipline;
- assignment of tasks taking into account the most important aspects of students in the implementation of project work;
- introducing a series of practical works that create leadership into the educational process..

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